

Improved thermal stability of antireflective moth-eye topography imprinted on PMMA/TiO₂ surface nanocomposites

Alejandra Jacobo-Martín,^a Jaime J. Hernández,^a Patricia Pedraz,^a Eduardo Solano,^b Iván Navarro-Baena,^a and Isabel Rodríguez^a

^a Madrid Institute for Advances Studies in Nanoscience (IMDEA Nanoscience), C/ Faraday 9, Ciudad Universitaria de Cantoblanco. 28049 Madrid, Spain.

^b ALBA Synchrotron, Carrer de la Llum 2-26,08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract

The thermal stability of antireflective moth-eye topographical features fabricated by nanoimprint lithography on poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) incorporating TiO₂ nanoparticles is explored. The effect of nanoparticle load on the relaxation dynamics of the moth-eye nanostructure is evaluated via grazing incidence small angle x-ray scattering (GISAXS) measurements by *in situ* monitoring the structural decay of the nanopatterns upon thermal annealing. It is demonstrated that the incorporation of TiO₂ nanoparticles to the imprinted surface nanocomposite films delays greatly the pattern relaxation which, in turn, enhances the stability of the patterned topography even at temperatures well above the polymer glass transition (T_g). The improved thermal behaviour of the antireflective films will significantly enhance their functionality and performance in light-trapping applications where temperatures typically rise, such as solar devices or solar glass panels.

Introduction

The fabrication of bioinspired multifunctional components based on polymers has experienced a vast growth in the last decades [1-4], being the antireflective (AR) surfaces based on moth-eye like textures among the most interesting structure-mediated functionalities [5]. These textures include sub-wavelength nanocone topographies that effectively create a graded refractive index interface capable of reducing Fresnel reflections and consequently increasing light transmission [6-9]. A number of possible applications for these topographic features have been reported, such as the implementation of flexible AR films onto electronic displays for glare reduction [10] or for light trapping and efficiency enhancement of solar devices [11, 12].

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3 Typically AR moth-eye patterns have been fabricated by nanoimprint lithography (NIL) on
4 polymer materials [10, 13]. There are two main variants of the NIL technique: UV-NIL and
5 thermal NIL (T-NIL). In the former case, the pattern is transferred from a mold onto a low
6 molecular weight resist layer using low pressure, and then crosslinked under UV light to render a
7 hard AR coating. In T-NIL, or hot embossing, a thermoplastic polymer is softened by increasing
8 the temperature (above its T_g) and mechanically deformed by a mold under pressure. The features
9 of the mold are filled in by a viscous polymer flow and a replica is finally obtained onto the
10 polymer surface upon cooling and demolding. Both processes are scalable via roll to roll (R2R)
11 processing and offer different advantages [14]. One of the main advantages of T-NIL, besides the
12 lower costs of thermoplastics compared to UV photoresines, is that the functional patterns can be
13 created on free standing films, avoiding compatibility problems due to the mismatch in optical,
14 thermal or mechanical properties when using coatings or layers of different materials [15].
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23 An important drawback in T-NIL is related to the inherent internal residual stress generated into
24 the nanoimprinted features during the process in which the polymer flows under elevated pressure
25 and under confinement conditions [16]. The induced residual stress during the nanoimprint
26 process may lead to pattern relaxation with associated dimensional changes and ultimately will
27 lead to pattern decay and deterioration of the replica fidelity [17, 18].
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31 In the case of thermoplastic surfaces nanostructured by NIL, pattern relaxation can be accelerated
32 when the imprinted substrates are subjected to heating. Pattern relaxation on thermally treated
33 substrates generally can take place by different driving forces acting on the nanopatterns. Firstly,
34 it may be triggered by internal stress relaxation [17, 19-21]. When films are subjected to heating,
35 the temperature increases nearing the polymer matrix T_g , a rubber like elastic recovery may take
36 place as a consequence of the storage modulus decrease, being this effect particularly significant
37 for polymers with high chain entanglement. With a further increase in temperature, the polymer
38 would enter into the viscous flow state. In this state, surface tension becomes the primary driving
39 force of pattern decay causing polymer material to slump or reflow which ultimately would cause
40 the patterns to retreat and finally flatten on to the surface [22, 23].
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47 Thermal reflow of polymer melt has been advantageously employed as smoothing method to
48 produce ultra-smooth optical structures such as microlens arrays [24, 25]. Nevertheless, the un-
49 controlled polymer reflow is typically an undesirable effect since it leads to deterioration of the
50 structural integrity of the patterns responsible for the functionality or the properties of the surface.
51 In terms of nanoimprinted surfaces, several studies have addressed the temperature dependence
52 structural stability of the patterns [17, 20] and different approaches have been attempted to
53 improve their stability and durability. For instance, surface photochemical crosslinking induced
54 under UV exposure or plasma treatment has been reported to enhance the thermal resistance [19].
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3 Other approaches based on the addition of nanofillers have also shown promising results in this
4 direction. From a practical point of view, the incorporation of nanoparticles into a polymer matrix
5 imparts additional properties which depend on the nature of the filler. Enhanced thermal or
6 electrical conductivity, mechanical stability, flame retardant or photoinduced self-cleaning
7 capabilities, among other properties can be achieved [26-29]. In addition, the nanometric size of
8 the fillers in polymer nanocomposites plays a significant role in modifying the physical properties
9 of the thermoplastic matrix as they are incorporated within the polymer chains [30]. The
10 confluence between the length scale of both, nanoparticles and polymer radius of gyration, leads
11 to an increment of the topological constrains and restriction of the polymer chains motion,
12 promoting the entangled dynamics in the polymer chains [31, 32]. This effect has been exploited
13 for the improvement of the creep resistance or for increasing the polymer T_g [33, 34] and the
14 suppression of the stress relaxation dynamics above the melting temperature of a poly (ethylene
15 oxide) matrix by the addition of a high content of silica nanoparticles has been reported [35].

16 The effect of nanoparticles on the stability of nanoimprinted nanocomposite patterns has been
17 investigated in several works by Bhadauriya *et al.* [36-38] The authors showed that the
18 stabilization of the imprinted nanostructures was due to the deceleration of the polymer relaxation
19 behaviour caused by loading polymer grafted nanoparticles (PGNP) or unmodified nanoparticles
20 onto the nanocomposite.

21 In this communication, we study and explore this effect in a real application for the enhancement
22 of the thermal stability of moth-eye AR functional surfaces. The enhanced thermal stability is
23 brought about by the incorporation of titania (TiO_2) nanoparticles to the imprinted surface and
24 formation of a surface nanocomposite moth-eye pattern. This enhancement is determined by
25 tracking the pattern decay of the moth-eye nanostructures *in situ* upon thermal annealing, via
26 grazing incidence small angle x-ray scattering (GISAXS) measurements. Notably, it is seen that
27 the nanocomposite AR surfaces preserve their antireflective functionality after being exposed at
28 temperatures far beyond the T_g of the PMMA matrix.

29 Previously, we have demonstrated the effect of TiO_2 nanoparticles as effective fillers for the
30 improvement of the mechanical resistance of the moth-eye nanotextured surface offering, in
31 addition, a photocatalytic activity and a self-cleaning action [28]. In this work, we further
32 demonstrate the improvement of the thermal stability as additional benefit offered by the PMMA/
33 TiO_2 surface nanocomposite AR topography.

Results

Nanostructured moth-eye nanocomposites films were produced by sequential processing steps of nanoparticle spin coating and soft T-NIL, as described in detail in the experimental section. Initially, TiO₂ nanoparticle dispersion is spin coated over the PMMA film which is subsequently imprinted to obtain a surface nanocomposite with imprinted moth-eye like nanostructure. For this, a dispersion of nanoparticles in methanol with a concentration of 0.5 wt.% was chosen based on previous results to obtain an optimum balance between transparency and mechanical reinforcement of the surface [28]. In contrast to conventional nanocomposites, fabricated in general by melt blending, solvent mixing or *in situ* polymerization [36-39] where the filler is distributed throughout the bulk. The present fabrication process gives rise, in one step, to a patterned surface nanocomposite with the nanoparticles concentrated at the surface on the moth-eye topography. Hence, this process represents a practical approach to produce reinforced functional surface nanotopographies, allowing for the matrix properties preservation (*i.e.* transparency, flexibility, etc.) while reducing processing steps and nanomaterials usage. Figure 1a shows the 3D scan reconstruction of a moth-eye nanostructured PMMA/TiO₂ surface nanocomposite obtained by AFM on tapping mode. The characteristic moth-eye like structures, consisting of a hexagonal array of nanocones, can be clearly identified. Figure 1b shows the scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of a PMMA/TiO₂ nanoimprinted film obtained using the secondary electrons (SE) detector and Figure 1c shows the SEM image corresponding to the same area, collected on the backscattered electrons (BSE) detector. In the case of BSE, the signal intensity is sensitive to the atomic number; hence, it shows brighter spots corresponding to TiO₂ nanoparticles (some of them are pointed by white arrows in the Figure). The image demonstrates the homogeneous distribution of nanoparticles over the whole nanoimprinted layer with an average height of the nanostructures of *ca.* 330 nm and a pitch of 250 nm. SEM images with higher magnification have been included in Figure S1.

Figure 1. (a). 3D AFM image reconstruction of a nanostructured moth-eye PMMA surface nanocomposites film. SEM images using the secondary electrons detector (b) and the backscattered electrons detector (c). The bright areas observed in (c) correspond to TiO₂ nanoparticles. White arrows point out some of the larger bright areas which corresponds to high TiO₂ content on the topography.

To assess the thermal stability of the nanoimprinted moth-eye AR nanocomposite surfaces, monitoring of the thermally induced pattern decaying process was analysed and compared to that of neat films by *in situ* temperature dependence GISAXS measurements.

Previous studies to capture in real time the pattern decay dynamics have been performed by *in situ* heated AFM measurements [37] with a time resolution of 1 second. However, this technique presents limitations in terms of scan size (10 μm) and therefore, in area that can be monitored. Laser diffraction has been also employed to monitor the decay of imprinted micrometric sinusoidal polymer patterns above the T_g through changes in the diffracted intensity of a laser beam impinging onto the structured surface [40]. Jones *et al.* tracked in real time the shape evolution of polymer nanostructures during thermal annealing using critical dimension small x-ray scattering (CD-SXAS).[20] Both techniques are based on the diffracted intensity related to the volume of the material which generates the electronic density contrast responsible of the scattering pattern. Hence, any pattern collapsing, or material reflow will cause the subsequent decrease of the scattered intensity that is being measured. Based on the same principle, GISAXS with the x-ray beam impinging at glancing angles ($< 1^\circ$) on the surface, provides improved statistical information from the larger areas ($\sim \text{mm}^2$) covered by the beam footprint, compared to other techniques ($\sim \mu\text{m}^2$) [41]. In addition, the high intensity of synchrotron radiation allows to capture in real time the relaxation processes and related structural evolution of the moth-eye topography upon heating at temperature well above the PMMA T_g . Thus, it is considered a practical tool for the evaluation of the nanoparticle effect on the pattern relaxation dynamics and related thermal stability.

GISAXS measurements were designed to assess the initial imprint fidelity and to track in real time the pattern decay of the moth-eye nanostructure during non-isothermal annealing. Figure 2a shows a scheme of the experimental setup geometry, describing the main axis and scattering angles used for the calculation of the scattering vectors q_x , q_y and q_z :

$$q_x = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\cos \omega \cdot \cos \alpha - \cos \alpha_i) \quad (1)$$

$$q_y = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\sin \omega \cdot \cos \alpha) \quad (2)$$

$$q_z = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\sin \alpha_i \cdot \sin \alpha) \quad (3)$$

where λ is the X-ray wavelength, α_i is the incidence angle and ω and α are the in-plane and out-plane exit angles, respectively. For the small exiting angles recorded by means of GISAXS, the q_x contribution is negligible ($q_x \approx 0$). The recorded GISAXS intensity (I) depends on the square of the form factor (F) and interference function (S): $I(q) = |F|^2 \cdot S(q)$. Therefore, due to the hexagonal symmetry of the nanocones array on the film surface, the intensity of the scattering pattern obtained is strongly dependent on the rotation axis ρ normal to the surface plane (*cf.* supporting video V1) where the combination of the form factor and interference function presents an intensity maximum. Figure 2b shows the characteristic 2D pattern obtained from a PMMA moth-eye nanocone topography at room temperature with the X-ray beam parallel to the 100 plane of the hexagonal array. The characteristic spacing of the 100 reflection of the hexagonal array was estimated from the position of the first scattering maximum observed by using the approximation $L \approx 2\pi/q_{y,max}$. The d-spacing value derived from the peak position, located at 0.0245 nm^{-1} , is in good agreement with the specified pitch for the AR moth-eye nanocones of 250 nm, being the outer maxima observed consecutive orders of the first one. Figure 2c shows the simulated 2D pattern of the moth-eye nanostructure, generated by employing the BornAgain software [42]. The simulation process, considering the input structural parameters and the simulated surface are further explained in the supplementary information (*cf.* Table S1 and Figure S2). After the refinement, the simulation results showed a good agreement with the experimental topographical parameters: a pitch of 230 nm and a height of 350 nm with the expected hexagonal lattice. Figure 2d shows the comparison of experimental and simulated 1D projections representing the scattering intensity obtained by the vertical integration of a section of 20 pixels, centered on the region corresponding to the Yoneda peak [43], where the maximum on intensity in q_z is located (*cf.* Figure 2c).

Prior to performing the temperature dependence measurements, the different substrates were carefully aligned to maximize the scattered intensity of the 100 reflection and its corresponding

diffraction orders, improving the pattern symmetry and allowing to compare the structural decay of the different samples during the temperature ramps (performed from 25 up to 150 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min). The moth-eye nanopattern decay was evaluated based on the analysis of the scattering vector q_y , which provides information about structural correlations parallel to the sample plane, according to standard analysis procedures reported earlier [41].

Figure 2. (a) Scheme of the experimental setup used for GISAXS measurements. The main rotational axis and scattering angles are indicated. 2D experimental (b) and simulated (c) GISAXS patterns obtained at constant incidence angle $\alpha_i=0.4^\circ$ with X-ray beam parallel to the 100 crystallographic axes of the hexagonal array. (d) 1D experimental (red) and simulated (black) normalized scattered intensity obtained from projections performed on the Yoneda peak region, marked with a red rectangle in (b).

Figure 3a shows the 1D integrated scattered intensity as a function of q_y , obtained during the heating ramps. At first sight, it can be appreciated a clear decrease in the number of visible diffraction orders above the PMMA T_g as a consequence of nanopattern distortion and degradation of the lattice perfection. In both cases the first maxima remain visible up to 155 °C indicating that the topography of the nanoimprinted surface is partially preserved even in the neat

polymer at the end point of the reflow. As mentioned, the existence of restricted polymer chains motions due to chain entanglements determine the thermal stability of polymer nanostructures above the T_g [19]. In this work, the molecular weight (M_w) of the PMMA employed (see Experimental Section) is *ca.* 10 times larger than the reported entanglement M_w of the polymer, which is about $10^4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ [44].

Figure 3b shows the integrated scattered intensity corresponding to the first maxima as a function of the temperature. The intensity drop observed can be ascribed to a decrease in nanofeature height as a consequence of the AR PMMA patterns decay at these high temperatures.[20] Remarkably, the intensity decay is strongly attenuated in the case of the titania reinforced nanostructures. Due to the short beam exposure times employed (0.5 s every 30s) thus, PMMA degradation due to radiation damage can be discarded.

Figure 3. (a) 1D integrated scattered intensity profiles as a function of q_y obtained during the heating ramp for the PMMA and PMMA/0.5% TiO₂ nanoimprinted surfaces. (b) Temperature dependence of the integrated scattered intensity of the 100 reflection (logarithmic scale). The dotted line indicates the bulk melting temperature of the PMMA matrix.

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3 The GISAXS results were confirmed by *ex-situ* atomic force microscopy measurements. Figure
4 4a shows the AFM topography images of the nanostructured films before and after the thermal
5 treatment. The characteristic hexagonal array of the moth-eye nanostructures can be identified
6 after heating in both the neat and nanocomposites substrates up to 150 °C. However, as it was
7 observed during the GISAXS measurements, the neat PMMA moth-eye pattern shows a
8 noticeable array distortion and nanocones thinning, with some of them laterally collapsing
9 (pointed by white arrows in Figure 4a). On the other hand, the moth-eye patterns on the surface
10 nanocomposite films remained in place and only a slight decrease in height was observed. The
11 graph in Figure 4a-right shows representative height profiles extracted from the two samples
12 before and after the thermal treatment. As it can be observed, the height mean value decreases
13 from *ca.* 330 nm at the initial stage, down to 70 nm in the case of neat PMMA (80 % decrease in
14 height). The height reduction is strongly prevented in the case of the surface nanocomposite,
15 reaching a final height of *ca.* 215 nm (35% decrease in height). These results agree well with the
16 *in situ* temperature dependence GISAXS measurements and serve to confirm the enhancement of
17 the thermal stability of the moth-eye PMMA nanopatterns by the incorporation of the titania
18 nanoparticles.
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Figure 4. (a) AFM topography images of PMMA and its TiO₂ surface nanocomposite nanoimprinted films at the initial stage (25°C) and after thermal annealing up to 150 °C. Representative height profiles corresponding to both substrates are shown on the right. (b) Specular transmittance spectra of antireflective PMMA and its nanocomposite films before and after sample heating up to 150°C. The flat PMMA spectrum is included as reference. (The spectral noisy discontinuities observed around 900 nm are due to the change in detectors in the spectrophotometer).

Due to the interrelation between surface nanostructure and surface functionality, the impact on the optical performance of the annealed AR films was next examined. Figure 4b shows the specular transmittance of the reference flat PMMA film compared with the nanostructured samples before and after thermal treatment. As can it be observed, the AR topography improves the transmittance values from *ca.* 90% of the pristine PMMA film up to *ca.* 95% for the neat

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3 PMMA AR film. This increment is slightly lower for the nanocomposite due to the large refractive
4 index of the TiO₂ nanoparticles incorporated in the layer resulting on a higher absorption [28],
5 nevertheless, the transmittance reaches 94% values on the nanocomposite PMMA AR film. After
6 heating the neat AR PMMA film up to 150 °C, the transmittance decreased to 91-92%, close to
7 the flat PMMA film. However, the AR PMMA TiO₂ surface nanocomposite film retained up to
8 93-94% of the film transmittance.
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14 It has been discussed before that the height and shape of the nanoscopic features that forms AR
15 layer has a direct impact on the optical performance of the films [45, 46]. In this case, the optical
16 performance obtained is in accordance with the topography profiles seen in Figure 4. As the height
17 of the PMMA moth-eye nanocones decreases after thermal treatment (*cf.* Figure 4a-top right), a
18 shorter path is available for the gradual reduction of the refractive index and as a result, the
19 antireflective effect is less efficient. However, in the case of the PMMA AR surface
20 nanocomposite, the resistance to the thermal reflow induced by the addition of nanoparticles,
21 allows to preserve to a large extent the height of the nanocones (*cf.* Figure 4a-bottom), and as
22 such, the optical transmittance of the films remained high even after thermal treatment at 150°C,
23 that is *ca.* 50 °C above the T_g of the PMMA.
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31 The results shown indicate that PMMA/TiO₂ surface nanocomposites can preserve to a large
32 extent the functionality of the nanoimprinted AR topography above the glass transition
33 temperature of the polymer matrix which will widen its usability in real applications. The
34 development of stable and durable nanopatterned surfaces is of great interest due to the broad
35 range of applications that could take advantage of the unique structure-mediated functionalities
36 that can be obtained. Particularly in the case of moth-eye AR solar cell covers, the increase in
37 thermal resistance is of high interests considering the elevated temperatures that can be reached
38 when the cells are exposed to the sun approaching the PMMA T_g in some cases [47].
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45 **Conclusions.**

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47 Moth-eye bioinspired antireflective surfaces were fabricated by soft T-NIL on PMMA/TiO₂
48 surface nanocomposites. The thermal stability of the moth-eye nanostructures was studied by in
49 situ GISAXS measurements whereby the structural decay of the nanopatterns was followed upon
50 thermal annealing. The analysis of the integrated scattered intensity obtained from the
51 nanotopography during the heating cycles revealed that upon addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles, the
52 thermal stability of the nanoimprinted polymer patterns is greatly enhanced. This effect was
53 observed even after thermal annealing at temperatures 50 °C above the PMMA T_g, observing that
54 the optical reflectance and transmittance of the moth-eye patterned films were unaltered only in
55 the case of the PMMA/TiO₂ surface nanocomposite AR films.
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3 The increase of thermal stability or resistance to thermal reflow in the nanoimprinted surface
4 nanocomposite patterns can be ascribed to the anchoring effect of the filler restricting the polymer
5 chain mobility thus, the pattern relaxation dynamics. This in turn allows for the preservation of
6 the functional moth-eye patterns at temperatures well above the softening point of the polymer
7 matrix, broadening the working temperature range of the AR polymer films.
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12 The results obtained suggest a simple, scalable, and cost-effective method to fabricate functional
13 topographies on surface nanocomposites with improved thermal stability far beyond the softening
14 temperature range of the polymer matrix.
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17 18 **Experimental**

19 20 21 Synthesis of TiO₂ nanoparticles

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23 TiO₂ nanoparticles were prepared via hydrothermal reaction of Titanium isopropoxide (IV)
24 (Acros organics) by using the procedure described before [28]. Briefly, 20 ml of this reagent was
25 added to 36 ml of deionized water and stirred for one hour at room temperature. After that, the
26 suspension was filtered through a Büchner kitasato system connected to a vacuum pump and
27 washed with about 2 l of deionized water. The white powder was placed into a teflon-lined
28 autoclave and mixed with 3.9 mL of 0.6 M tetramethylammonium hydroxide (Sigma Aldrich).
29 The solution was heated at 120 °C in an oven for 14 hours and subsequently centrifuged two times
30 (10 minutes at 10000 rpm) to remove aggregates. The crystalline structure of the nanoparticles
31 was characterized by synchrotron 2D wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) measurements.
32 Characteristic diffraction peaks of two different phases of TiO₂ were identified: anatase (87%)
33 and brookite (13%), both with photocatalytic activity[48] (see Figure S3 and Table S2 in
34 supporting information). The phase content was estimated from the peaks integrated intensity
35 ratio as reported elsewhere [49].
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45 The nanoparticle size (ACS) was estimated calculated by using the Scherrer formula: $ACS =$
46 $\frac{k \cdot \lambda}{\beta \cdot \cos \theta}$, where k is the shape factor (~0.9), λ is the wavelength (0.1 nm), β is the peak broadening
47 (FWHM in radians) and θ is the Bragg angle of the reflection [50]. The particle size was estimated
48 to be *ca.* 12 nm, in agreement with AFM height profile measurements (*cf.* Figure S4). In this case,
49 the real diameter is estimated from the height of the nanoparticles rather than from the lateral
50 dimensions, avoiding tip convolution overestimation [51]. The nanoparticle size was confirmed
51 by SEM (*cf.* Figure S5).
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Mold fabrication

A soft working mold was produced on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) by soft-lithography replication of a commercial nickel master mold with the moth-eye topography (HT-AR-02, Temicon). For this, a thin layer of hard PDMS (h-PDMS) was first used to fill the moth-eye nanocone cavities, onto which a thick layer of soft PDMS (s-PDMS) was poured to produce a flexible composite mold. To prepare the h-PDMS, the recipe was adapted from H. Schmid *et al.* and optimized in order to replicate the moth eye pattern with high accuracy. Vinyl and hydrosilane prepolymers (7-8% Vinylmethylsiloxane - dimethylsiloxane copolymer trimethylsiloxy terminated and Methylhydroxisiloxane - dimethylsiloxane copolymer respectively, ABCD GmbH) were used. 6 μl of a catalyst (platinum-divinyltetramethyldisiloxane complex in vinyl terminated poly (dimethylsiloxane), ABCR GmbH) and 100 μl of a modulator (1,3,5,7-tetravinyl-1,3,5,7-tetramethylcyclotetrasiloxane 97%, ABCR GmbH) were firstly mixed to 3.4 g of the vinyl compound, and then 1 g of the hydrosilane was added. The mixture was degassed under vacuum and then casted onto the nickel master mold. After 15 minutes filling the cavities, the remaining polymer was eliminated by gravity. The mold was placed in an oven at 80 °C under vacuum for 20 minutes to only achieve a partial cured layer. Subsequently onto this layer, 50 g of s-PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning) precursor supplemented with the initiator mixture (10:1) was poured and completely cured at 80 °C for 24 hours obtaining a PDMS composite mold of about 3 mm in thickness. The fabrication process is outlined in Figure S6.

Preparation of PMMA/TiO₂ nanostructured surface nanocomposites

PMMA (Sigma Aldrich, $M_w=120.000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) thin films were prepared over two different substrates: polyethylene terephthalate (PET) films (Hifi industrial films, 125 μm thickness) and polished silicon wafers (University Wafers, test grade). PET was chosen for being one of the most widely used substrate materials in flexible electronics and photovoltaics due to its transparency and chemical resistance [52]. Silicon was used for the samples subjected to thermal treatment and X-ray characterization by synchrotron radiation. Prior to polymer coating, O₂ plasma treatment was applied (150 ml/min, 50 W, 1 min) on the substrates. Then, a PMMA solution (7.5% w/w) in anisol (Scharlau Chemicals & Reagents) was spin coated (1000 rpm) onto the substrate. Next, the sample was placed on a hot plate (90 °C, 1 min) to evaporate the residual solvent. This process created a PMMA thin film over the PET of 460 nm in thickness as estimated by profilometry using a Dektak XTL Stylus Profiler (Bruker).

For the fabrication of the AR nanocomposite surfaces, the aqueous dispersion of TiO₂ ($\approx 24 \text{ wt}\%$) was diluted with methanol (Scharlau Chemicals & Reagents) at a concentration of 0.5 wt%, and then, spin coated (3000 rpm) over the PMMA thin films prepared previously. Then a soft T-

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3 NIL step was performed using an Eitre 3 Nanoimprint System (Obducat) whereby the prepared
4 substrates were imprinted at 180 °C applying a pressure of 45 bar for 5 min. Prior to demolding,
5 the substrates were cooled down to room temperature.
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8 9 Characterization of AR PMMA/TiO₂ composite films

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11 Nanostructured films were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using an Auriga
12 FIB-SEM system (Zeiss) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) in tapping mode using a
13 NanoWizard II (JPK) and a Multimode 8 AFM with a Nanoscope V controller (Bruker). The SEM
14 tool employed has a local charge compensation system based on injecting N₂ gas which allows to
15 obtain images directly from the nanoimprinted samples without any coatings. Due to the
16 hexagonal symmetry of the nanocone array it has been demonstrated that the sample orientation,
17 respect the detector plane, has a strong influence on the appearance of the SEM images [53]. All
18 samples were imaged at equivalent rotation angle using a 45° tilted sample holder to allow for a
19 direct comparison AFM measurements were performed using Tap300GB-G probes (Budget
20 Sensors) with tip radius < 25 nm and a nominal spring constant of 40 N/m.
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24 Specular transmittance and total reflectance were measured using a Lambda 950 UV-Vis
25 spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer), fitted with a 150 mm integrating sphere. Both parameters were
26 measured from 400 nm to 1700 nm wavelength range, at two different positions within the same
27 the sample.
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31 X-ray scattering techniques using synchrotron radiation were used in order to complete the *ex-*
32 *situ* and *in-situ* thermal characterization of TiO₂ nanoparticles and PMMA/ TiO₂ nanoimprinted
33 surfaces. 2D Wide Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS) and Grazing Incidence Small and Wide-
34 Angle X-ray Scattering (GISAXS) measurements were performed at the BL-11 NCD-SWEET
35 beamline of the ALBA synchrotron, Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain. An X-ray beam with
36 wavelength $\lambda=0.998$ Å was set using a Si (111) channel cut monochromator and collimated with
37 an array of Be lenses. The beam dimension at the sample position was estimated to be 40 μm
38 height and 100 μm wide. The 2D patterns were recorded with a Pilatus3 S 1M area detector (pixel
39 size 172x172 μm^2) for GISAXS and a Rayonix LX255-HS detector (pixel size 44.27x44.27 μm^2 ,
40 binning 2x2) for the 2D WAXS measurements. The scattering vector q for the wide [small] angle
41 scattering experiments was calibrated using chromium oxide (Cr₂O₃) [silver behenate] obtaining
42 a sample to detector distance of 100.4 [7615] mm. Incidence angles (α_i) were varied between 0.1
43 and 0.4°. Heating ramps we accomplished from 25 °C up to 150 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min
44 using a calibrated Linkam® TMS600 heating stage adapted for grazing incidence experiments.
45 The 2D WAXS data obtained was reduced to a 1D profile using Fit2D software [54].
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